

CoARA Boost Cascade Funding Call 2

BUDGET - Use of Resources Template

PARTNER'S NAME: Associazione Ricercatori in Sanità - Italia (ARSI)

PROJECT'S NAME: Impact-based assessment of the translational research in the Italian research hospitals

The use of the Resources Template is mandatory –This Use of Resources Template must be entirely filled and uploaded as a single PDF file (merged together with the Application Form) on the online SmartSimple platform.

MAXIMUM GRANT AMOUNT 12.406,81 €

TOTAL DIRECT COSTS 12.406,81 €

STAFF COSTS 7.729,00 €

Staff member role <i>For GDPR purposes, please do not include full names</i>	Actual cost/ Unit cost	Role in the project	€/ month rate	nb of Person Month	Total cost - staff
President	Unit cost	Coordinator	2620	1,55	4.061,00 €
President	Unit cost	Trainer	2620	0,8	2.096,00 €
Secretary	Unit cost	Administrative	2620	0,3	786,00 €
Board member 1	Unit cost	Administrative	2620	0,3	786,00 €
					0,00 €
					0,00 €

TRAVEL COSTS 2.503,95 €

Description of the travel purpose inc stimated date (project's month)	Who? Destination?	Cost / person / travel	Nb of persons	Nb of travels over the project's period	Total other cost
Networking with the european community Science4Policy	Coordinator - Rome	185,8	1	1	185,80 €
Engagement with the representative at the Ministry of Health	Coordinator - Rome	210,72	1	1	210,72 €
Kick-off meeting - M3	Coordinator and board	141,9	8	1	1.135,20 €

Networking with the european community Building capacity	Coordinator - Bruxelles	140,85	1	1	140,85 €
Trainings - M4	Trainer - Milano	48,24	1	1	48,24 €
Trainings - M6	Trainer - Milano	140,79	1	1	140,79 €
Trainings - M6	Trainer - Roma	642,35	1	1	642,35 €
					0,00 €
					0,00 €
					0,00 €
					0,00 €

OTHER DIRECT COSTS - purchases and services					2.173,86 €
Description of goods or services planned	Purpose / potential provider	Unit Cost	Nb of units purchased	Total other cost	
Kick-off room rental & catering	Hosting the kick-off meeting and facilitate the net	1272,46	1	1.272,46 €	
Kick-off printings	Informative material for the kick-off attendees and	101,9	1	101,90 €	
Website	Promotion of the CoARA project	720	1	720,00 €	
Training printings	Material printing for the M6 training	79,5	1	79,50 €	
				0,00 €	

SIGNATURE & STAMP

Scientific team

Name: Valeria Elisa Contarino

Date : 25/06/2025

Signature

Finance department

Name: Paolo Caravaggi

Date : 25/06/2025

Signature

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